

Phyllonorycter alpina (FREY, 1856) (Lepidoptera: Gracillariidae) in the Bieszczady Mts.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4518689>

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ABSTRACT. *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY, 1856) (Lepidoptera: Gracillariidae) in the Bieszczady Mts.

Phyllonorycter alpina is known from only a single site in Poland. Tenanted mines were found on *Alnus alnobetula* in the summit region of the highest part of the Bieszczady Mts. It is supposed that its occurrence is only a temporary event, and colonization may occur periodically from the adjacent areas of the Eastern Carpathians.

KEY WORDS: Lepidoptera, Gracillariidae, *Phyllonorycter alpina*, *Alnus alnobetula*, Bieszczady Mts.

INTRODUCTION

Phyllonorycter HBN. is a large genus of leaf mining moths with about 400 described species worldwide (DE PRINS & DE PRINS 2005). In Poland it is represented by 62 species (BUSZKO 2017). Most of the Polish species live on trees and shrubs and only a small share is associated with herbaceous plants. Monophagy or oligophagy is dominant in host plant preferences. One of the monophagous species occurring in the mountains is *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY). Its larva lives on *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K. KOCH (= *Alnus viridis* (CHAIX) DC) (Fig.4). The typical form of the species occur in higher elevations in the mountains, usually above tree line. It was found, however, also in lower elevations of about 550 m a.s.l., where it is represented by an ecological form *hauderiella*, which differs from the typical form in paler coloration of the forewing, but is uniform in genitalia structure (GREGOR & POVOLNÝ 1950). The main area of the distribution is concentrated within the Alps, where the species was found in all countries: Austria, France, Italy, Germany and the Switzerland. Also it is known from southern Czech Republic, Ukraine and Romania. The species has recently been reported from Poland (BUSZKO 2017). Details of the discovery are provided here.

MATERIAL STUDIED

Out of five collected mines only two adult specimens were reared (Figs. 1, 2). The specimens are stored in the author's collection.

1♂ FV23 Bieszczady Mts., Halicz, 1310 m, e.l. 14 II 2013, J. Buszko leg.; larva 10 IX 2012, *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K. KOCH.

1♀ FV23 Bieszczady Mts., Tarnica, 1330 m, e.l. 10 II 2013, J. Buszko leg.; larva 10 IX 2012, *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K. KOCH.

FAUNISTIC COMMENTS

Phyllonorycter alpina (FREY) has since long been expected to occur in the Bieszczady Mts. It is the only region in Poland where green alder, its host plant, does occur in natural stands. Occurrence of green alder is rather scarce and restricted to the highest ranges of the Bieszczady Mts. All previous search attempts did not bring positive results. First in 2012 several mines were found on small bushes in the summit areas of Halicz and Tarnica, which make the highest part of the Bieszczady Mts. Underside mines are situated between lateral veins, usually extending from the midrib to the leaf margin. The lower side of the mine is yellowish green with long prominent folds. Upper side is yellowish with slight marbled pattern (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) – adults: 1 – male, 2 – female (photo J. Buszko).

Ryc. 1. *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) – motyle: 1 – samiec, 2 – samica (fot. J. Buszko).

Fig. 2. The mine of *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) on *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K. KOCH (photo J. Buszko).

Ryc. 2. Mina *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) na *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K. KOCH (fot. J. Buszko).

Due to very limited range of green alder, the occurrence of *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) in the Polish part of Bieszczady Mts. may only be temporary. It is probable that the species may colonize the site occasionally by immigration from higher parts of the Eastern Carpathians. In the adjacent area the species was found on the Hoverla Mount in Chornohora in Ukraine (BIDZILYA & BUDASHKIN 2004).

Fig. 3. *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K. KOCH – a host plant of *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) in its environment (photo J. Buszko).

Ryc. 3. *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K. KOCH – roślina pokarmowa *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) w jej środowisku (fot. J. Buszko).

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Streszczenie

Phyllonorycter alpina (FREY, 1856) (Lepidoptera: Gracillariidae) w Bieszczadach

Phyllonorycter alpina (FREY) znany jest w Polsce tylko z Bieszczad. Nieliczne miny znalezione we wrześniu 2012 na olszy *Alnus alnobetula* (EHRH.) K.KOCH

w najwyższych partiach połonin w pasmach Halicza i Tarnicy. Z min wyhodowano dwa okazy motyli. Pomimo wielokrotnych poszukiwań we wcześniejszych latach min nie udawało się znaleźć. Wskazuje to na możliwość okresowego zasiedlania Bieszczad przez *Phyllonorycter alpina* (FREY) z sąsiadujących terenów Karpat Wschodnich, gdzie liczne występowanie min stwierdzono na Howerli w Czarnohorze.

Accepted: 3 February 2021; published: 8 February 2021

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